

Challenges of Special and Inclusive Education for Autistic Students in Higher Education

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RESUMO

A educação especial e inclusiva ainda é um assunto pouco debatido, o direito à aprendizagem para todos na sociedade, diferenciando-se apenas o atendimento de acordo com as diferenças individuais do aluno e a consciência de que só através dela é que a inclusão social é de fato garantida, ainda tem pouco escopo. O presente estudo visa evidenciar a importância, as dificuldades e as estratégias pedagógicas adotadas para a aplicação da educação inclusiva e especial. Trata-se de uma pesquisa bibliográfica na qual serão analisados artigos e publicações científicas de forma a reunir as pesquisas de forma sistemática e ordenada, contribuindo para o aprofundamento do conhecimento do tema investigado, acompanhando as principais etapas da pesquisa. De acordo com a pesquisa, percebe-se que a educação inclusiva, apesar de ser um tema bastante conhecido na teoria, sua implementação é bastante insatisfatória, o que dificulta a inserção de pessoas com diagnóstico de autismo na sociedade.

Colovesical fistula: An updated pathological approach

ABSTRACT

Special and inclusive education is still a little debated subject, the right to learning for everyone in society, with only the service differing according to the individual differences of the student and the awareness that it is only through it that social inclusion is in fact guaranteed, it still has little scope. The present study aims to highlight the importance, difficulties and pedagogical strategies adopted for the application of inclusive and special education. It is a bibliographic research in which scientific articles and publications will be analyzed in order to gather research in a systematic and orderly manner, contributing to the deepening of the knowledge of the investigated theme, following the main stages of the research. According to the research, it can be seen that inclusive education, despite being a well-known theme in the theory, its implementation is quite unsatisfactory, which makes it difficult for people diagnosed with autism to enter society.

INTRODUÇÃO / INTRODUCTION

Education aimed at students with special needs, previously adopted as a parallel model, that is, only for them, has been

adopted in mainstream schools in recent decades, which is called inclusive education (GLAT; PLETSCHE; FONTES, 2007).

When talking about inclusion, it is important to know how to distinguish this concept in two dimensions: essential inclusion and elective inclusion. Essential inclusion understands that all citizens are entitled to participate at all levels of services offered to society (education, leisure, health, culture, etc.) regardless of their need. In addition to the essential inclusion, the elective is defined as an inclusion without the formation of taxing groups, such as, for example, people with or without disabilities, and that people can relate to according to their interests regardless of whatever your condition (FREITAS, 2008).

Thus, inclusive education is configured as a democratic, social and political action that is based on the right of all students to have access to education without any type of discrimination (BEYER, 2006). This concept was consolidated as from 1964, in a world conference on special education, which resulted in the Salamanca Declaration, where guidelines were instituted with the aim of reformulating both the political and the educational ones that favor social inclusion. The Salamanca Declaration ensures that people with special needs are part of the state's educational system (ANDRADE; GOMES, 2012).

The National Policy on Special Education in the Perspective of Inclusive Education, presented in 2007 by the Ministry of Education in partnership with the Secretary of Special Education, proposed guidelines for inclusive education to reach all levels of education (from early childhood education to higher education) ensuring the continuity of studies to people with different needs, whether they are: disabilities, giftedness or developmental disorders (BRASIL, 2007).

Seen as a preventive form of social exclusion and an important instrument for inclusion in society, it is through the implementation of inclusive / special education and mainly through the training of teachers, that the guarantee of special education at all levels, educational service specialized, greater family participation and greater accessibility in communication and information, are guaranteed. Among students with special needs in higher education, the work highlights students with developmental disorder: Autism, which involves difficulties in both skills and social life, but the cognitive impairment changes according to the stimuli that this individual acquires throughout of your life (BOSA, 2006).

Thus, it will be possible to emphasize the importance of inclusive education as a form of development and stimulation for the autistic student, to demonstrate that educating an autistic student involves in addition to public policies or elimination of prejudice, it also involves the training of teachers and focuses on the contribution to understand the perceptions and feelings that teachers have about the inclusion of students with special educational needs. This is an important aspect to achieve the objective of an inclusive education, the participation of teachers, principals, since they make up the educational system. Thus, according to the changes that are being proposed, it is necessary that there is a qualification of this professional, for the success of his intervention before the student (SANT'ANA, 2005).

The objective of this study is to highlight the main difficulties of higher education teachers in the face of students with special educational needs and what are the pedagogical strategies adopted in view of this situation.

THEORETICAL REFERENCE

Inclusive education in the education system and teacher training

According to Mendes (2006), the history of special education has its origins in the 16th century, by means of professionals who began to observe that special people considered unfit for education, had the potential to learn, and started to initiate this process of education. Later with the school becoming compulsory and at the same time being unable to educate all students, special classes emerged where the "disabled" were sent.

Between the end of the 80s and the beginning of the 90s, parents and people with special needs began to manifest the idea that it would be necessary for special education to be fully integrated, as until then it was treated with reduced attention. Access to education was slowly being achieved, along with education for the general population (SANCHEZ, 2005).

Andrade and Gomes (2012) point out that, from then on, social inclusion began to receive more attention by governments to combat exclusion, idealized initially in Europe in 1990, where member states of the European Union adopted several measures with the objective of combating exclusion.

As a result of one of the many measures adopted, UNESCO held in 1994, in Salamanca, Spain, the World Conference on Special Educational Needs: access and quality. As a result of this conference, he obtained the document Declaration of Salamanca, which is considered one of the most important in terms of inclusive education. In that statement came the concept of "People with Special Educational Needs", which refers to children and young people who have some learning difficulties. It also reinforces that educational institutions should receive them regardless of their conditions (Brasil, 1997). Through the Salamanca declaration, there was a need for socio-educational transformations, thus contributing to the consolidation of inclusive education.

Brazil followed this worldwide trend, but in an isolated way without being linked to general education. In the 50's, there was a negligence of the government and, consequently, the non-provision of the service, this gave rise to private philanthropic schools to serve these unassisted people. The government came to pay more attention to this issue only in the 70s, however, it is still estimated that the vast majority of special students are out of the classroom (MENDES, 2006).

Inclusive education is included in the Brazilian education policy but attempts to minimize school exclusion do not overcome the elements that generate educational inequality, as they are linked to social dynamics. Knowing this, it is necessary to guarantee that education is the right of all and must thus be integral, in that it is understood that special education must achieve with responsibility, promote and develop the learning of these students (FERREIRA, 2015).

In the Federal Constitution of 1988 (Brazil, 1988) and in the Guidelines and Bases of National Education - Law no. 9.394 / 96 (Brasil, 1996) education is a right of all and that the preferential service in the regular school system must be people with disabilities. However, the legislation does not oblige

schools to provide this service and even allows this education to be carried out only in special schools.

Special education is understood, according to Art.3 of the National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education:

School educational process defined by a pedagogical proposal that ensures special educational resources and services, organized institutionally to support, complement, supplement and, in some cases, replace common educational services, in order to ensure school education and promote the development of the potential of students who have special educational needs, in all stages and modalities of basic education. (BRAZIL, 2001).

The inclusion of students with disabilities or educational needs in the educational context has been constantly discussed, which has resulted in mechanisms for regulating the inclusion process that guarantee the equal rights of these people, such as the inclusive education policy (EI) (FARIAS; MARANHÃO ; CUNHA, 2008).

The term inclusion in Education, by itself, is characterized by the exclusion of any student from the academic field. Institutions that follow an inclusive education policy develop means for each student to build knowledge without discrimination (FREITAS, 2008). It involves the participation, in addition to human resources and materials, of all the professionals of the institution and even of the other students to make changes flexible, outline class strategies and course plans aimed at inclusion (FERRARI; SKEL, 2007).

One of the aspects to achieve the objective of an inclusive education, is the participation of teachers, principals, since they make up the educational system. Thus, according to the changes that are being proposed, it is necessary that there is a qualification of this professional, for the success of his intervention before the student (SANT'ANA, 2005).

It is necessary to offer different strategies to pass on the content, in a satisfactory way to achieve learning. Technological innovations facilitate the communication relationship with people with special educational needs, enabling the minimization of difficulties. However, there are people who may have difficulties due to their limits, such as: difficulty in access, navigation or because they do not understand the information (NUNES; BRAUN; WALTER, 2011).

Training a teacher requires an understanding of behavior and the attitude that the teacher should have, according to different spaces, times and people. Since the end of the 1970s, many of these conducts have been revised, and the concern to train reflective professionals, with critical capacity and educational transformations, has intensified. individual reality, so there is no single way of how work will be organized, one must take into account the uniqueness of each person (MOURA, 2009).

The development of the person with autism can achieve higher levels of progress, through the performance of the teacher, through the intervention of stimuli and the student, because when exposed to stimuli without the intervention of the teacher, they can become stressed because of a lot of information which culminate in insufficient learning (FARIAS; MARANHÃO; CUNHA, 2008).

Guiding a person with special needs means teaching according to differences, respecting the needs of each one and they need to know how to teach them at different levels of education. However, the lack of training and structure, implies difficulties in conducting this class, so it is necessary to invest in training, post-graduation, development in research on people with special needs, in order to learn more about the subject. It is necessary that all members of the education system plan actions in an integrated and collective way for the improvement and continuity of teaching to these students in higher education (SANT'ANA, 2005).

Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) and Higher Education

Bechtold and Weiss (2005) define as people with physical, sensory and intellectual impairment, temporary or permanent, who produce losses in interaction with society and therefore need different ways to establish such interaction.

Autism is classified as Invasive Developmental Disorder (TID), characterized by the atypical development of behavior, and repetitive movements may occur. Usually diagnosed at three years of age, with the perception of impairment limitations in social interaction, behaviors and communication that evolve according to development (CAMARGO; BOSA, 2009).

According to Klin (2006) apud Kanner (1943) the first cases were reported in 1943, by Leo Kanner and were called autistic disorder of affective contact. In these cases, there was an inability to relate to other people and unusual responses to the environment. For a long time he did not know how to explain the etiology of autism, it was believed that it could be the result of a bad relationship with his parents. , due to these various deficits. Epidemiological studies indicate that autism is identified in 1 in 200 people, being more common in boys (KLIN, 2006).

After the classification made by Leo Kanner, autism began to be studied more and more, which enabled a new perception about diagnosis and treatment at the time it was discovered. Increasingly the identification of autism, and its cause has been evolving, being more researched and expanding knowledge about the disorder (MESQUITA; PEGORARIO, 2013).

According to the Guidelines for Attention to the Rehabilitation of People with Autistic Spectrum Disorders (ASD) (2014), the following defining characteristics of this condition are: difficulty in developing relationships, delay in language, mainly echolalia, repetitive games, lack of imagination however have good mechanical memory and normal physical appearance.

Autism is characterized by a chronic condition that can become disabling, according to its manifestation. He appears at 36 months and triggers a series of events (social, economic, emotional) for both the family and society (NIKOLOV; JONKER; SCAHILL, 2006). It is a syndrome, to this day, unexplainable, in which a relationship difficulty occurs and is accompanied by deficits (language, learning and social pattern), as these are acquired, due to social interaction (FREITA, 2008)

In order to diagnose autism, at least six fundamental criteria from three groups must be followed: Qualitative impairment in

social interactions; Qualitative impairment in communication and repetitive and stereotyped restrictive patterns of behavior, identification and activities, as well as the identification of disturbances in the social fields, imaginative play in the early years of life (KLIN, 2006).

Understanding the types of autism can help teachers develop these students with special needs. Autism can be classified as classic autism (diagnosed before the age of three, mainly presenting problems in communication, social interaction and repetitive behaviors and this type can vary from mild to severe functioning) and Asperger's Syndrome (characterized by exceptional verbal skills; Invasive Disorder of the Development and childhood disintegrative disorder) (BRASIL, 2014).

Access to higher education by people with special educational needs has shown a great evolution. The importance of the teacher in the inclusion process of the disabled person was recognized, especially with regard to autism, which requires recognizing his level of intellectual development so that he can guide to levels not yet reached, developing his intellectuality (FARIAS; SPIDER- SPIDER; CUNHA, 2008).

However, only the entry of students with autism into higher education does not guarantee that inclusion occurs. The needs of this student must be met throughout their academic life (admission, permanence and exit from higher education) and also involves the means of transfer of content, interaction with the university community and the different pedagogical strategies (FERREIRA, 2015).

With regard to people with disabilities in higher education, although some institutions encourage the permanence of these students in higher education courses, there are still obstacles to the implementation of inclusive education, such as non-adaptation in the university, if there are no alternative forms, outside the traditional, evaluation, methods that will be taught in the discipline and especially the teacher's training. Commitment influences the teacher-student relationship (MATOS, 2007).

METODOLOGIA / METHODOLOGY

This study was based on a bibliographical research in the collection that was found published in relation to the theme of study. The integrative review aims to gather and synthesize research results on a delimited theme or question, in a systematic and orderly manner, contributing to the deepening of knowledge of the investigated theme (MENDES; SILVEIRA; GALVÃO, 2008).

It was considered in its construction that in the process of elaboration of an integrative review it is necessary to go through 06 distinct and sequential steps: identification of the theme and selection of the hypothesis or research question for the elaboration of the integrative review, establishment of criteria for inclusion and exclusion of studies/ sampling or search in the literature, definition of information to be extracted from selected studies / categorization of studies, evaluation of studies included in the integrative review, interpretation of the results and presentation of the review / synthesis of knowledge (GIL, 2010).

To carry out the research, a search was made in scientific articles in the following databases: SCIELO, VHL-BIREME, referring to the theme, in the period from 2005 to 2015, using the descriptors: autism, education, inclusive education.

For the selection of sources, the following inclusion criteria were considered: articles indexed in the selected databases, with adhered descriptors, whose publication was carried out in the period from 2005 to 2015, in the Portuguese language, and which provided a full text. As exclusion criteria: Articles that did not provide full text (abstract only), which did not include the study period, online articles not available in full and that did not have the focus addressed.

From this search, an analysis of the data was performed through an exploratory reading of all selected material and finally a reading in the entire text was performed with the purpose of verifying the contribution of each study to the development of the research and to the resolution of the following research problem: What are the main difficulties faced by teachers in the construction of the teaching-learning process of an autistic student? And from then on reach the expected goal.

After reading the selected articles, the results were analyzed, arranged in a table for better understanding and interpretation and then distributed into categories.

RESULTADOS & DISCUSSÃO / RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 1: Distribution of scientific journals according to: the year, methodology and journal of publication.

Variables	N	%
period		
2005 a 2006	9	27,2
2007 a 2008	11	33,3
2009 a 2010	4	12,1
2011 a 2012	5	15,1
2013 a 2014	2	6
2015	2	6
Methodology		
Qualitative	11	33,3
Quantitative	4	12,2
Literature review	18	54,5
Publication journals		
St. Louis Orione Magazine	1	3
Special Education Journal	1	3
Magazine. Brazilian Psychiatry	4	12
Psychology and society magazine	4	12
Brazilian magazine of special education.	5	15
Text Context Nursing	1	3
Journal of the Health Sciences Institute	1	3
Educate Magazine	1	3
Summus Editorial Editor	1	3
Inclusion Magazine	1	3
Journal of the Brazilian Society of Speech Therapy	2	6
other	5	15

Source: SCIELO database, VHL-BIREME

Table 1 presents the general distribution of the articles studied (period, methodology, journals of publication), expressed in frequency and percentage.

We can see from the results of Table 1, that the majority of publications were in 2007/2008 with 11 publications (33.3%), which can be noted for few publications on the subject in recent years.

The literature review with 10 articles (47.6%) due to the fact that it is a research method that allows the search, evaluation, and organization of available research on the subject, its final objective is knowledge of the theme, the implementation of new ideas, and the identification of problems that will guide future research (MENDES; SILVEIRA; GALVÃO, 2008).

In relation to the type of journal, most publications are from the Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry and the Journal of Special Education (18.75%), which have the purpose of publishing original works, mainly aimed at clinical updating.

According to Chart 2, it can be noted that most of the publications surveyed refer to the theme Inclusive education (20), addressing the implementation, inclusive policies and especially the perception of subjects directly linked to this theme. Publications addressing autistic disorder (09) addressed general characteristics, the main signs for diagnosing the syndrome. Other themes related to methodological concepts obtained 07 publications.

Based on the distributions of the articles, the studies were analyzed and organized into categories to better understand the information found in the selected collection. They are: People with Special Educational Needs and inclusion in the education system and what pedagogical method adopted in the face of inclusion in education.

Table 2: Distribution of publications including authors, title, subject.

Author	Title	Subject
ANDRADE, R.S.B.; GOMES, H.T.	Inclusive education: Perspectives of the Salamanca declaration.	Contribution of the regular school in the education of special people and its reflection in society.
BECHOT, P.; WEISS, S.	The inclusion of people with special educational needs in the labor market.	Reflection of school inclusion in the labor market
BEYER, H.O.	Inclusive education: reframing concepts and practices of special education.	Accessibility to education and its different practices
BOSA, C.A.	Autism: Psychoeducational Interventions	Interventions that have been used in the treatment of autism.
Brazil. Ministry of Education.	National Education Council. National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education.	Guidelines to ensure the perspective and universalization of education.
Brazil. Ministry of Health.	Department of Health Care Department of Strategic Programmatic Actions. Guidelines for Rehabilitation Care for People with Autism Spectrum Disorders	Guidelines for multidisciplinary teams for the care of autistic people and their families.
Brazil	Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil.	Guaranteeing citizens' rights and avoiding social inequalities.
Brazil. Ministry of Justice.	Salamanca Declaration and Lines of Action on Special Educational Needs	Government policies and actions on the inclusion of people with special needs in regular schools.
BRENTANI, H.; PAULA, C.; BORDINI, D.; ROLIM, D.; SATO, F.; PORTOLESE, J.; PACÍFICO, M.	Autism spectrum disorders: an overview on diagnosis and treatment	Early identification and multiple treatment modalities for autism.
BRAGIN, J.	Antecedent of autistic education in Brazil: political theories and their influences on pedagogical practices in specialized educational care centers.	Importance of the formulation of education policies and their importance in educational centers.
CAMARGO, S.P.H.; BOSA, C.A.	Social competence, school inclusion and autism: a critical literature review.	Concept of social competence studies currently existing in the area of autism and school inclusion.
FARIAS, I.M.; MARANHÃO, R.V.A.; CUNHA, A.C.B.	Teacher-student interaction with autism in the context of inclusive education: analysis of the teacher's mediation pattern based on the Theory of Mediated Learning Experience.	Discussion on the professional practice of two teachers and their children with autism in early childhood education classes.
FERREIRA, V.C.M.F.	School Evaluation of Autistic Students: a study on the school-family relationship in a public educational institution in the city of Belém-Pará.	Evaluation of the process of construction of school learning of autistic students, from the perspective of the school-family relationship.

Table 2 (continue)

FERRARI, M.A.L.; SEKKEL, M.C.	Inclusive education in higher education: a new challenge.	Aims to discuss the challenges of inclusive education in higher education.
FREITAS, N. K.	Socio-educational inclusion in school: evaluation of the process and students.	Evaluation of inclusive public policies and how this implementation in practice.
GESCHWIND, H.A.	Advances in autism	Study autism, its causes and progress in research.
GUEDES, N.P.S.	The Brazilian scientific production on autism in Psychology and education.	How autism affects individual education and learning.
GIL, A.C.	How to develop research projects.	Methodological standards for the development of research projects
GLAT, R.; PLETSCH, M. D.; FONTES, R.S.	Inclusive education & special education: proposals that complement each other in the context of school open to diversity.	Implementation of Inclusive Education in Brazil and the impact on society of this policy.
KANNER, L.	Autistic Disturbances of affective contact.	Main features of autistic syndrome.
KLIN, A.	Autism and Asperger's Syndrome: An Overview.	Main features of Asperger syndrome and Autism.
MATOS, N.D.	The policy of special education in the state of Sergipe.	Implementation and verification of special education in the state of Sergipe.
MENDES, K.D.S.; SILVEIRA, R.C.C.P.; GALVÃO, C.M.	Integrative review: research method for the incorporation of evidence in health and nursing.	Characteristics of autism syndrome and its identification as a child.
MENDES, E.G.	The radicalization of the debate on school inclusion in Brazil.	Debate on inclusive education policy.
MESQUITA, W.S.; PEGORARO, R.F.	Diagnosis and treatment of autistic disorder in Brazilian publications: literature review.	Characteristics of autistic disorder and scientific production of the subject.
MOURA, E.P.G.	Management of teaching work: the "dramatic" use of ones.	How the teacher's work is developed, being an important role in the student's learning.
NIKOLOV, R.; JONKER, J.; SCAHILL, L.	Management of teaching work: the "dramatic" use of ones	Teacher's role regarding the role of trainer, main difficulties and standardization of educational activities.
NUNES, L.R.O.;	Autism: psychopharmacological treatments and areas of interest for future developments.	Characteristics of autistic disorder and major treatments.
BRAUN, P.; WALTER, C.C.F.	Teaching procedures and resources for students with disabilities: what has been disseminated in the work of ANPED GT 15 on these topics?	Research on inclusive education for students with disabilities.
RODRIGUES, D.	Inclusion and Education: twelve views on Inclusive Education.	Debate on different ways of implementing inclusive education.
SANT'ANA, I.M.	Inclusive education: conceptions of teachers and principals	Importance of inclusive education from the point of view of teachers and principals.
SANCHEZ, P. A.	Inclusive education: a means of building schools for all in the 21st century	Critically analyze the inclusion of people with special needs in regular Brazilian education, considering social and legal aspects, through a literature review.
SILVA, F.T.; GONÇALVES, E.A.V.; ALVARENGA, K.F.	Inclusion of people with special needs in regular education: literature review.	Insertion of students with special needs in regular education.
SONZA, A. P.; SANTAROS, L.	Virtual Environments Accessible from the Perspective of Visually Impaired Users.	How virtual environments help develop special people.
TAMANHA, A.C.; PERISSINOTO, J.; CHIARI, B.M.	A brief historical review on the construction of the concepts of Childhood Autism and Asperger's syndrome.	Features of autism and asperger syndrome.
VITTA, F.C.F.; ALEXANDRA, S.R.	Perception of early childhood education teachers about the inclusion of children with disabilities	Relationship between student teacher and methodological strategies for the child's learning.

Source: VHL, BIREME, SCIELO, BRAZIL.

People with special educational needs and inclusion in the education system.

The reduction of inequalities has been an increasingly controversial issue in recent times, because for many it can no longer be admitted that in such evolved and globalized times there is still this type of inequality. Inclusive education throughout the historical process has presented progress and setbacks, today emerges as a new social reality through the insertion of all students, especially students with special educational needs, in regular school without any kind of discrimination (SILVA; GONÇALVES; ALVARENGA, 2012).

With regard to education in relation to people with disabilities, including autistic people, many studies indicate that the development of activities directed at these people varies according to the degree of commitment, for a better understanding of knowledge (BRAGIN, 2011).

Inclusive education supports the disabled in a special education that is aimed at these pupils. However, it must be admitted that education systems are not always prepared to receive these students and their diversities, being very dependent on organizations and philanthropic entities. Inclusion is far from immediate responses, perspectives and challenges for the concrete implementation of education are observed (GUEDES, 2015).

The right to participate in social life is guaranteed to every citizen, in this point of view the right to education and in particular to higher education is included. However, this right has often not yet been put into practice. The barriers these students face limiting their learning in an HEI are remarkable (RODRIGUES, 2008).

According to Matos (2007) special education requires that all educational institutions at their different levels should review/remake their organization, means of evaluation and teaching schedule mainly and, if not more importantly, the continued training of their educators. Although it is still a process very tied to prejudices, discrimination, it is noted in its late and slow way the insertion of these individuals in this process in which they were suppressed.

According to the Ministry of Education, through Ordinance No. 1,793/94 Art.2, is recommended in addition to the inclusion of content on ethical, political and educational aspects of society as well as the integration of people with disabilities in higher education courses, taking into account their specificities (BRASIL, 1994).

The National Policy for the Integration of Persons with Disabilities, under the provisions of Art. 27, says that higher education institutions (HEIs) must offer adapted tests, as well as the support that the student needs, for example, time to carry out the same (BRASIL, 1989).

According to Freitas (2008) access to higher education has increased in recent years, although it is not yet very expressive, when compared to the number of students entering universities. It also states that these institutions must be prepared for students with disabilities, providing all the means for them to develop successfully in the course, even in the face of the constant objections present around the world, because there are

divergences in the way inclusion is perceived, preventing the goal of inclusive policies from being achieved.

Difficulties and the importance of the implementation of Special Education in the Education System

Educational institutions, through the reception of people with special needs, contribute to the insertion of these people in society and especially in the labor market. According to Rodrigues (2006) this reception should take into account individual characteristics of the citizen, restructuring of school practices, taking into account that everyone is able to learn, these spaces of education should promote the elimination labels and standardized behaviors.

Regarding this restructuring, it includes professionals who should work with these students through the training of teachers, not only by conducting a course, but also in investing research to better deepen the type that the professional is with (RODRIGUES, 2006).

Vitta and Alexandra (2010) highlight the importance of certain professionals to work in special education, such as the Physical Educator, Psychologist, Speech Therapist, Physiotherapist and Occupational Therapist.

The National Education Plan for people with special educational needs considers people with physical, hearing, visual, intellectual and people with global developmental disorder (TGD) and that special education should reach all levels of education. The support of colleagues and all the faculty, new lesson strategies, are of great importance for inclusion (FERRARI; SEKKEL, 2007).

However, the challenges in higher education become greater. The student with disabilities, especially the autistic, takes longer to perform their activities, causing a lot of emotional distress (SONZA; SANTAROS, 2008). Data indicate that 70% of autistic people have mental retardation, which is an aggravating factor: the inclusion of the disabled with mental retardation is not mandatory for educational institutions, which makes access to the university even more difficult (TAMANHA; PERISSINOTO; CHIARI, 2008).

There are many obstacles that the autistic student faces, one can mention: Social interaction, due to characteristics of the disorder, such as the difficulty in understanding complete rules, not liking physical contact and not being able to maintain a conversation; The restricted interest that prevents them from going ahead in learning; emotional vulnerability, not knowing how to deal well with the demands of a course, getting stressed and frustrated, because they could not follow the class; The **lack of concentration, through distractions**, disorganized or through repetitive behaviors and still has to overcome the prejudice and discrimination suffered by society (BRENTANI et al., 2013).

In this sense, institutions have to offer means to reduce or mitigate these natural obstacles of students. The observation of this student, encouraging work in groups, offering additional explanation, performing activities with different times, avoiding sudden changes in environments, not some measures that can be adopted to contribute even more to this insertion,

teacher concern should turn to how to pass on the content contributing to advances and avoid the abandonment of higher education (GESCHWIND, 2009).

The effects of educational inclusion is to convince all citizens that the rights provided for in the constitution must be respected. It is to ensure that people with disabilities participate in activities both academic and in the community, bringing benefit both to the disabled (improving their reasoning, understanding rules and being accepted and society) as well as the extinction of prejudices, discrimination and violence, also educating society.

CONCLUSÃO / CONCLUSION

Autism is characterized by an Invasive Developmental Disorder (TID), in which it is usually identified at the age of three and is characterized by the developmental deficits of this person with autism. The way it manifests depends on the level of commitment it is in, ranging from isolation with little social interaction to the highest degree of interaction, whether or not it can be maintained.

It is believed that the inclusion of autistic students in the education system and the continuity of this teaching can develop it both socially and intellectually. However, it is a goal that is being achieved at slow pace, because there are still some barriers ("fear" on the part of the teacher, lack of structure of the institution, change of curricula, etc.) for the definitive and integral implementation of inclusive and special education.

It is understood, therefore, that little research is done on the inclusion of people with special educational needs, despite being a well-known and debated subject for many years. Therefore, importance should be given to the perception that both students and teachers have on this topic, considering suggestions for solutions to problems, developing a work aimed at finding solutions for the consolidation of inclusive education.

REFERÊNCIAS / REFERENCES

- ANDRADE, B.S.; GOMES, H.T. Inclusive education: perspectives of the salamanca declaration. *Revista São Luis Orione*, v.1, n.6, p.37-48, Jan/Dec. 2012. Available in: <http://www.catolicaorione.edu.br/portal/wpcontent/uploads/2015/01/Educa%C3%A7%C3%A3o-Inclusive-Revista-5%C3%A3o-Luis-Orione-v-1-n-6-jan-Dec-2012.pdf>. Accessed 5 August 2016.
- BECHOT, P.; WEISS, S. The inclusion of people with special educational needs in the labor market. Monograph (psychopedagogy) - Instituto Catarinense de Pós Graduação. Santa Catarina. 2005.
- BEYER, H.O. Inclusive education: resignifying concepts and practices of special education. In: *Inclusion - Special Education Magazine*. v.2, n.2, Jul/2006. Available in: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbee/v12n2/a10v12n2>. Accessed 10 August 2016.
- BOSA, C.A. Autism: Psychoeducational interventions. *Rev. Bras. Psiquiatr.* v.28, supl. 1, p.547-33.2006. Available from: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbp/v28s1/a07v28s1.pdf>. Accessed August 18. 2016.
- BRAZIL. Ministry of Education. National Board of Education. National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education. Cne/CEB Opinion n.02/2001. Available in: <http://portal.mec.gov.br/cne/arquivos/pdf/CEB0201.pdf>> Access on 4 June 2016.
- BRAZIL. Ministry of Saúde. Department of Health Care Department of Strategic Programmatic Actions. Guidelines for Rehabilitation Care of People with Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD). Brasília- DF. 2014. Available in: http://bvsm.sau.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/diretrizes_atencao_reabilitacao_pessoa_autismo.pdf. Accessed 26 Sep. 2016.
- BRAZIL. Mec. Secretariat of Special Education. Subsidy document to the Inclusion Policy. Brasília: SEESP, 2007. Available in: http://peei.mec.gov.br/arquivos/politica_nacional_educacao_especial.pdf. Accessed 18 August 2016.
- BRAZIL. Ministry of Justice. Statement of Salamanca and Lines of Action on Special Educational Needs. Brasília: CORDE, 1994. Disopable in: <http://portal.mec.gov.br/seesp/arquivos/pdf/salamanca.pdf>. Accessed 18 August 2016.
- BRAZIL. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil. Brasília, DF: Senate. 1988.
- BRAZIL. Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education. Law No. 9,394 of December 20, 1996. Official Gazette of 23 December 1996.
- BRENTANI, H.; PAULA, C.; BORDINI, D.; ROLIM, D.; Sato, F.; PORTOLESE, J.; PACIFIC, M. Autism spectrum disorders: an overview on diagnosis and treatment. *Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry*. v. 35, p. 62-72. 2013. Available at: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1516-44462013000500008. Accessed 5 Nov. 2016.
- BRAGIN, J. Antecedent of autistic education in Brazil: political theories and their influences on pedagogical practices in specialized educational care centers. *Digital Fermentario Magazine*. v. 5, p.1-22. 2011 Available at: www.fermentario.fluice.edu.uy/index.php/fermentario/article/view/60/17. Accessed 5 Nov. 2016.
- CAMARGO, S.P.H.; BOSA, AC Social competence, school inclusion and autism: a critical review of the literature. *Psycho. Soc. Florianopolis*, v.21, n.1, Jan. /Apr. 2009. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0102-71822009000100008. Accessed 20 September 2016.
- FARIAS, I.M.; SPIDER, R.V.A.; CUNHA, A.C.B. Teacher-student interaction with autism in the context of inclusive education: analysis of the teacher's mediation pattern based on the Mediated Learning Experience Theory. *Rev. Bras. educ. spec.* v.14, n.3, p.365-384. 2008. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1413-65382008000300004&script=sci_abstract&tlng=pt> Access 7 June 2016.
- FERREIRA, V.C.M.F. School Evaluation of Autistic Students: a study on the school-family relationship in a public educational institution in the municipality of Belém-Pará.2015.181p. Postgraduate (educational sciences) - Federal University of Pará. Para: UFP, 2015.
- FERRARI, M.A.L.; SEKKEL, M.C. Inclusive education in higher education: a new challenge *Psicol. Cienc. Prof.* v.27 n.4 Brasília. 2007. Available at: http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1414-98932007001200006> Access on 10 June 2016.
- FREITAS, N. K. Socio-educational inclusion in school: evaluation of the process and students. *Essay: Aval Pol Públ Educ.* v.60, n.16, p.323-60. 2008. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S010440362008000300002&script=sci_abstract&tlng=pt. Accessed: 7 Nov.2016.
- GESCHWIND, H.A. Advances in autism. *Annual review of medicine*. v. 60, p.367-380.2009. Disponivel em: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3645857/>. Acesso 14 Nov. 2016.
- GUEDES, N.P.S. The Brazilian scientific production on autism in Psychology and education. *Psic. Content and pesq.* Brasília. v.31, n.3, p.303-309. Jul/Sep. 2015. Available in:

- <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/ptp/v31n3/1806-3446-ptp-31-03-00303.pdf>. Accessed 8 Nov 2016.
20. GIL, A.C. How to Develop Research Projects. 4Ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2010.
 21. GLAT, R.; PLETSCHE, M. D.; FONTES, R.S. Inclusive education & special education: proposals that complement each other in the context of school open to diversity. *Education, Santa Maria*, v. 32, n. 2, p.343-356. 2007. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_nlinks&ref=000158&pid=S1413-6538201400030001100017&lng=pt. Accessed August 18. 2016.
 22. KLIN, A. Autism and Asperger syndrome: An overview. *Rev Bras Psiquiatr.* v.28, n.supl 1. p. 3-11.2006. Available in: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbp/v28s1/a02v28s1.pdf> Access on 10 July 2016.
 23. MATOS, N.D. The policy of special education in the state of Sergipe (1979-2001). *Rev Bras. Educ. Espec.* v. 13, n.1, p.77-94. 2007. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S141365382007000100006&script=sci_abstract&tng=pt. Accessed 20 Nov.2016.
 24. MENDES, K.D.S.; SILVEIRA, R.C.C.P.; GALVÃO, C.M. Integrative review: research method for the incorporation of evidence in health and nursing. *Text Contexto Enferm. Florianopolis*, v.17, n.4, Oct/Dec. 2008. Available in : <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/tce/v17n4/18.pdf>. Acesso em 26 out.2016.
 25. MENDES, E.G. The radicalization of the debate on school inclusion in Brazil. *Brazilian Journal of Education*. V.11, n.33, Sep/Dec.2006. Available in: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbedu/v11n33/a02v1133.pdf>. Accessed 23 August 2016.
 26. MOSQUE, W.S.; PEGORARO, R.F. Diagnosis and treatment of autistic disorder in Brazilian publications: literature review. *J. Health Sci. Inst.*v.31, n.3, p. 324-9. 2013. Available in: https://www.unip.br/comunicacao/publicacoes/ics/edicoes/2013/03_jul-set/V31_n3_2013_p324a329.pdf. Accessed 3 Oct 2016.
 27. MOURA, E.P.G. Management of teaching work: the "dramatic" use of one's. *Rev. Educate.* n.33, p.157-169. 2009. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_abstract&pid=S0104-40602009000100011&lng=pt&nrm=is&tng=en. Accessed 15 September 2016.
 28. NIKOLOV, R.; JONKER, J.; SCAHILL, L. Autism: psychopharmacological treatments and areas of interest for future developments. *To see. Bras. bras. Psycheder.* v. 28, n.1, p. 39-46. 2006. Available in:< http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1516-44462006000500006&script=sci_abstract&tng=pt> Access on 10 June 2016.
 29. NUNES, L.R.O.; BRAUN, P.; WALTER, C.C.F. Teaching procedures and resources for students with disabilities: what has been disseminated in the work of ANPED's GT 15 on these topics?. *Rev. Bras. Educ. Spec., Marília.* v.17 no.spe1 May/Agost. 2011. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1413-65382011000400004. Accessed 5 Sep 2016.
 30. RODRIGUES, D. Inclusion and Education: twelve views on Inclusive Education, *Summus Editorial*, v.4, n.2. Sao Paulo. 2006. Available at:< http://redefinclusao.web.ua.pt/docstation/com_docstation/21/fl_47.pdf> Access on 14 June 2016.
 31. SANCHEZ, P. A. Inclusive education: a means of building schools for all in the 21st century. *Inclusion Magazine. Brasília*, v.1, n.1, Oct./2005, p. 718. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_nlinks&ref=000168&pid=S1413-6538200900010000700017&lng=pt. Accessed 23 August 2016.
 32. SANT'ANA, I.M. Inclusive education: conceptions of teachers and principals. *Psicology under study. Maringá.* V.10, n.2, p.227- 234, May/Aug.2005.Available in: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/pe/v10n2/v10n2a09.pdf>. Accessed August 27, 2016.
 33. SILVA, F.T.; GONÇALVES, E.A.V.; ALVARENGA, K.F. Inclusion of the disabled person with special needs in regular education: literature review. *J. Soc. Bras. Speech audiol.* São Paulo v.24, n.1. 2012. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2179-64912012000100017. Accessed Nov. 17. 2016.
 34. SONZA, A. P.; SANTAROS, L.; COMFORT, D. "Virtual Environments Accessible from the perspective of visually impaired users". In: *SBIE 2008 - XIX Brazilian Symposium on Informatics in Education.* Fortaleza - CE. 2008.
 35. TAMANHA, A.C.; PERISSINOTO, J.; CHIARI, B.M. A brief historical review on the construction of the concepts of Infantile Autism and Asperger's syndrome. *Rev Soc. Bras. Bras. Speech-language Audiol.* v. 13, n.3, p.296-9. 2008. Available in: <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rsbf/v13n3/a15v13n3>. Accessed 25 Oct 2016.
 36. VITTA, F.C.F.; ALEXANDRA, S.R. Perception of early childhood education teachers about the inclusion of children with disabilities. *To see. Bras. bras. Educ. Spec.* v. 16, n.3, p. 415-428. 2010. Available in: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1413-65382010000300007. Accessed Nov 17, 2016.